

ORTHO-SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYLS

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2-Chloro-, -bromo-, -iodo- and -cyano-diphenyls as well as the magnesium compound of 2-iododiphenyl have been prepared. A method for the preparation of the magnesium compound of 2-chlorodiphenyl has been described.

Mono-*ortho*-substituted diphenyl halides can form the starting material for the synthesis of a number of *ortho*-substituted diphenyls, whose preparation has so far either not been attempted at all or is possible only through tedious methods giving poor yields. While there are a number of references available for the method of preparation of 2-iododiphenyl (Gilman and others, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51,2260; Mascarelli and others, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, II, 2713) there are only meagre data existing for the preparation of 2-bromo- and 2-chloro-diphenyl (Mascarelli, *loc. cit.*). Using 2-aminodiphenyl as the parent substance these compounds have been prepared by the Sandmeyer's reaction in satisfactory yields.

Of the three *o*-substituted diphenyl halides, only the iodide reacts readily with magnesium to give the Grignard reagent under usual conditions. Owing to the liberation of large quantities of iodine the use of magnesium derivative of *o*-iododiphenyl for the synthesis of other *ortho*-substituted derivatives of diphenyl by the Grignard reaction is inconvenient. Attempts to prepare by the usual method the magnesium compounds of the corresponding bromo and chloro derivatives have, however, been unsuccessful.

A good yield of the magnesium derivative of 2-chlorodiphenyl has, however, been obtained by heating together magnesium flakes with 2-chlorodiphenyl in an evacuated and sealed hard glass tube at 210-215°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Chlorodiphenyl.—A solution of 2-aminodiphenyl (21g.) in 10 c. c. hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) was diazotized by sodium nitrite solution (10g. in 20 c. c. water). The solution was added to a freshly prepared cuprous chloride solution, prepared from 18g. of copper sulphate. When the evolution of nitrogen ceased, the solution was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and distilled in steam. The distillate was extracted with ether and the ether extract dried and after removal of ether the product was distilled at 154°/12.5 mm., yield 24g. (60%). D_{20}^{25} , 1.1499. It solidifies to colourless crystals, m. p. 31°. (Found: C, 76.52; H, 4.81; Cl, 18.88. $C_{12}H_9Cl$ requires C, 76.49; H, 4.77; Cl, 18.83 per cent).

2-Bromodiphenyl.—A solution of 2-aminodiphenyl (21g.) was diazotized and treated with cuprous bromide solution, prepared from 16 of copper sulphate. The product was isolated as in the previous case and a yellow oil obtained, b.p. 160°/11 mm.

D_{20}^c , 1.2175, yield 18.7g. (65%). (Found : Br, 34.15. $C_{12}H_9Br$ requires Br, 34.30 per cent).

2-Iododiphenyl.—A solution of 2-aminodiphenyl (21g.) was diazotized and treated with a solution of potassium iodide (30g. in 300 c. c. water). The iodo compound was isolated as usual. A light yellow oil, b. p. 181°/21 mm., yield 24.3g (70%). $D_{27.3}^c$, 1.6031. (Found : I, 45.51. Calc for $C_{12}H_9I$: 45.34 per cent).

2-Cyanodiphenyl.—A solution of 2-aminodiphenyl (20g.) was diazotized and the solution treated with cuprous cyanide solution prepared from 35 g. of copper sulphate. When evolution of nitrogen ceased the solution was warmed for half an hour on a water-bath, made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and then distilled in steam. The distillate was first shaken with stannous chloride solution to remove any yellow azo-dye formed and then the tin was precipitated with sodium hydroxide solution. It was then extracted with ether and the ether extract dried and distilled. It was obtained as a yellow oil, b. p. 174°/13 mm., yield 11.0 g (50%). On keeping it in a refrigerator for a week the oily liquid crystallised to faintly coloured needle shaped crystals, m. p. 37°. (Found : C, 87.18 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 7.68. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9N$: C, 87.14 ; H, 5.03 ; N, 7.82 per cent). 2-Cyanodiphenyl was prepared by Knorr (*Annalen*, 1928, 464, 34) and also by Braun (*ibid.*, 1929, 468, 273).

Magnesium derivative of 2-Iododiphenyl.—A solution of 2-iododiphenyl (7.0g.) in absolute ether (70 c. c.) and magnesium flake (0.7g.) was refluxed with stirring in an inert atmosphere of hydrogen for about 2 hours. After the reaction was complete, the quantity of magnesium compound formed was determined. The solution was made up to 100 c. c. with absolute ether. 10 C. c. of this solution were hydrolysed by boiling with 150 c. c. of water and 20 c. c. standard sulphuric acid. The excess of acid was titrated against standard sodium hydroxide according to the method described by Gilman and Meyer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 159). The quantity of magnesium compound is about 80% of the theory.

Magnesium derivative of 2-Chlorodiphenyl.—Magnesium flakes (0.8 g.) and 2-chlorodiphenyl (5 g.) were heated together in an evacuated and sealed hard glass tube (1.0 cm. bore) for 6 hours in an air-bath at 210-15°. After the reaction was complete, the contents of the tube were dissolved in 100 c.c. of absolute ether and the percentage yield determined as in the previous case. yield 32% of theory.